

D4.3 Quantifying the influence of Open Access on innovation and patents

Observing and Negating Matthew Effects in Responsible Research and Innovation Transition

D4.3 - Quantifying the influence of Open Access on innovation and patents
Version 1.0
PUBLIC

We investigate to what extent Open Access publications were cited in patents. Drawing on publicly available big data sources, including Google Patents and Unpaywall, we present a patent citation analysis dedicated to the Open Access status of scientific non-patent references. Our findings suggest an Open Access citation advantage in patents, but show variation across technology sectors and countries.

ON-MERRIT - Grant Agreement 824612

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement no 824612.

Document Description

D4.3 - Quantifying the influence of Open Access on innovation and patents

D4.3 Quantifying the influence of Open Access on innovation and patents			
WP4 - Innovation and Industry			
Due date	30 September 2021	Actual delivery date:	30 September 2021
Nature of document	[Report]	Version	1.0
Dissemination level	Public		
Lead Partner for deliverable	UGOE		
Authors	Najko Jahn, Thomas Klebel, David Pride, Tony Ross-Hellauer		
Reviewers	Petr Knoth, Thomas Klebel		

Revision History

Issue	Item	Comments	Author/Reviewer
V 0.1	Draft version	For initial review	Najko Jahn, Thomas Klebel, David Pride, Tony Ross-Hellauer
V 0.2	Review	Review	Petr Knoth, Thomas Klebel, Tony Ross-Hellauer
V 1.0	Final Version	Revision and integration of reviewer's input	Najko Jahn, Thomas Klebel, Tony Ross-Hellauer

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Executive summary

Open Science policies aim at improving the discovery, access and re-use of research not only within the scientific community, but also within broader society, for instance to promote technology. Yet, the extent to which openly available scientific work impacts technological inventions remains largely unknown. Building on work carried out in D4.1 and D4.2, we combine publicly available data sources about patents and scholarly publications to explore uptake of Open Access to scientific literature cited in patents. In doing so, we expand existing patent citation analysis methodologies in order to provide evidence about the use of Open Access resources in innovation.

Our key observations are:

- Investigating over 22 million patent families indexed in Google Patents, we found that around one third were supported by at least one citation to non-patent literature. However, the number of references per patent family can vary considerably across technological sector and inventor countries, which is in accordance with previous research.
- Focusing on scientific articles cited in patents, we found an Open Access citation advantage, suggesting that openly available research articles are more likely cited in patents than closed access work. In line with the general trend, Open Access uptake grew over the years, with nearly half of cited articles published between 2008 and 2020 being openly available. In line with research on both technology-science linkage and Open Access, we found considerable country and subject specific variations. Particularly patents representing inventions from the US and the UK cited disproportionately more often Open Access work.
- Expanding on D4.2 we observed the use of preprints, not only from the well-established arXiv in the Physical and Material Sciences including Engineering, but also in the Biological and Life Sciences, where preprints have become a widely used Open Science practice to accelerate communication about COVID research.

In line with previous research on the value of patent citation analysis, it is challenging to link our results to specific science policies and incentives. Although more and more scientific resources become openly available, it must be assumed that the discovery of relevant resources to innovation can still be resource-intensive for inventors and examiners alike. We furthermore recommend that follow-up research and monitoring exercise take advantage of a growing evidence base associated with patent citations and Open Science evidence.

1 Introduction

Open Science policies aim at improving the discovery, access and re-use of research not only within the scientific community, but also within broader society. Catalysing innovation is a major goal in this latter regard (EISabry 2017). Yet, the extent to which openly available scientific work impacts technological inventions remains largely unknown. Here, we combine publicly available data sources about patents and scholarly publications to explore uptake of Open Access to scientific literature cited in patents. In doing so, we expand existing patent citation analysis methodologies in order to provide evidence about the use of Open Access resources in innovation.

According to the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), “a patent is an exclusive right granted for an invention”, which, along with a technical documentation, must be publicly disclosed as a patent application. To support claims, patents refer to other patents (patent-to-patent citations) and, to a lesser extent, to other types of work, termed as non-patent literature (NPL) by the WIPO and large patent offices. The majority of NPL citations is to scholarly literature, also referred to as scientific non-patent-references (SNPR), while NPL can also include references to technical documentations or reports (van Raan 2017).

For more than 40 years, SNPR have been studied as an indicator of science-technology interactions. In their pioneering work, Carpenter, Cooper & Narin (1980) motivated patent citation analysis as an approach to determine the value of basic research to the economic, societal and technological development of a country. Since then, an increasing body of research has drawn on SNPR to study various aspects of the linkage between science and technology. Likewise, evaluative patent citation analysis has become a monitoring tool to support policy-making.¹

Here, we apply patent citation analysis to measure the extent to which Open Access resources were mentioned in patents. Only a few studies so far particularly focused on Open Access to SNPR. Drawing on a combination of publicly available big data sources, we present a general overview of Open Access to SNPR. Hence, this deliverable does not aim at specific research questions, but rather provides an initial investigation of potentially meaningful patterns using descriptive statistics.

The outline is as follows. First, we review the existing evidence base relative to patent citation analysis, describing specific characteristics of NPL in general and SNPR in particular. Then, we present our data analytics workflow, which makes use of Google Patents to find and extract NPL. By matching to big scholarly data sources, we were not only able to analyse not the NPL coverage, but also to explore potential discrepancies in the Open Access uptake to SNPR.

¹ A prominent example are the Patent Landscape Reports from the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) https://www.wipo.int/patentscope/en/programs/patent_landscapes/
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2 Background

Within this report, we investigate to what extent Open Access publications were cited in patents. To provide context, we hence briefly summarize the empirical evidence associated with scientific non-patent references (SNPR), how this citation practice differs from that in scientific writing, and existing evidence regarding Open Access and Open Science uptake in patents, as well as relevant methodological approaches towards patent citation analysis.

2.1 Role of patent citations to scientific literature

Citation practices in scientific writing and patenting differ. In science, only authors are expected to cite all relevant work, whereas in patenting, both inventors and examiners are legally obliged to support claims made in the patent application through citations (van Raan 2017). Particularly, US patent law requires that the patent examiner carefully selects references (Tijssen 2001). Also, the European Patent Convention demands that examiners consult a variety of scientific literature and include documents, which are considered as most relevant (Verbandt & Vadot, 2018). However, evidence suggests that most citations are made by the inventors themselves. In a large-scale study of patents from the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) issued after 2001, Ahmadpoor & Jones (2017) found that while examiners were responsible for 36% of patent-to-patent citations, they only contributed 4% of NPL.

SNPR should not be interpreted in every case as constituting the key sources of an invention, but rather as indicative for a spectrum of science-technology interactions, ranging from signalling the “awareness of scientific results” to considerable direct contributions to the innovation (Tijssen 2001). Drawing on patents from the field of nano-scale technologies, Meyer (2000) investigated the impact of scientific results on innovation through patent citation analysis. The author found that SNPR mainly represent the more general background of an invention, rather than a direct link. Based on interviews with a sample of 33 Belgian inventors active in nano-technology, biotechnology and life science about their motivation to cite SNPR, Callaert, Pellens & Van Looy (2014) confirmed that SNPR rarely reflect the role of research as a source of inspiration for technological invention. Around 30% of patents with a strong link to scientific activities lacked citations. If available, inventors rated 40% of SNPR as background, while 27% were considered as very important. 9% were rated as unimportant. As a consequence, SNPR should not be interpreted as evidence for a direct link between scientific work and technological invention. To draw such conclusions would require the qualitative examination of patents and SNPR, ideally in conjunction with querying the inventors about their citation motivation (van Raan 2017).

2.2 Characteristics of patent citations to scientific literature

Research has revealed important trends in patent citation practices. First of all, a highly-skewed distribution of NPL has been observed across studies, with a large proportion of patents lacking any references at all (van Raan 2017). Examining a patent sample from the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) and the European Patent Office (EPO) between 1996 and 2001, Callaert et al. (2006) estimated that 55% (USPTO) respectively 64% (EPO) of NPL are SNPR published in journals. There is, however, conflicting evidence concerning coverage across journals. While Guerrero-Bote, Moed, & De-Moya-Anegón (2021) estimated that

within five years, patent citations cover one third of Scopus-indexed journals, van Raan's (2017) comprehensive review found that SNPR appeared only in a small group of journals. In another work on "sleeping beauties", publications whose impact (in terms of citations) is not immediate but grows over time, van Raan & Winnink (2018, 2019) noticed a considerable time-lag between an SNPR' publication date and the patent application. The authors note, however, that the lag has shortened over the years, which the authors suggest is attributable to inventor-author self-citations. In another recent patent citation analysis, it was found that scientific articles which made a novel contribution to a field, are significantly more likely to have a technological impact measured by SNPR (Veugelers & Wang 2019).

There are also studies investigating the link between the country affiliation of an invention and the cited SNPR. Examining SNPR in US patents, Narin, Hamilton & Olivastro (1997) found that inventors cited a large proportion of scientific articles that were authored in their own country at prestigious universities and laboratories, and were funded by the important research funders National Science Foundation (NSF) and National Institutes of Health (NIH). In a recent large-scale study of patents related to innovations in biomedicine, Ke (2020) confirmed the dominance of scientific articles linked to research funded by the US government and the NIH in particular. Investigating the situation in the Netherlands, Tijssen (2001) observed an increasing proportion of Dutch-invented patents that cite domestic research, particularly driven by author-inventor self-citations and patents from large multinational firms from the technology sector like Philips. Cross-country comparisons need to take national citation practices into account in the interpretations of their findings, which are governed by the respective patenting law as well as the availability of literature (Callaert et al. 2006).

As in scholarly communication, patent citation analysis revealed field-specific differences. Investigating 1,088,650 life science and biomedicine patents, Ke (2020) reports large variations among the different technology sectors in terms of SNPR coverage. In particular, biotechnology and drug patents had an above-average SNPR uptake and growth rate. Similarly, Hötte, Pichler & Lafond (2020) observed an increase of SNPR among patents targeting low-carbon energy technologies. This increase was dominated by the sub-fields "Biofuels and Fuels from waste", "Solar PV" and "Nuclear fusion science-intensive", while innovations related to "Hydro" and "Geothermal" energy technologies had a comparatively lesser SNPR share. Because of the evidence of varying SNPR uptake rates among patents, the number of SNPR is a widely considered indicator to measure the "science intensity" of a field of innovation (van Vianen, Moed & van Raan 1990). However, an econometric model based on survey responses and several indicators for the patent value, including patent classification and patent family size, suggests that SNPR might be only informative for some fields (Harhoff, Scherer, Voipe, 2003).

2.3 Open Access to scientific non-patent references (SNPR)

While an increasing body of research focuses on Open Access to scientific research articles (Pinfield 2015, Piwowar 2018, see also ON-MERRIT D3.2 "Cumulative Advantage in Open Science and RRI: A Large-Scale Quantitative Study", forthcoming), only a few studies have thus far examined the specific impact of Open Access on innovation using SNPR, indicating the importance of our present study. Bryan and Ozcan (2020) investigated a sample of 43 medical and biotechnology journals published between 2005 and 2012. Similar to the effect on public sector research (Staudt 2021), they found a modest increase of citations to NIH-funded research after the introduction of the NIH Open Access policy, while citation rates to non-funded research stagnated. Focusing on small biotechnology companies, Bryan and Ozcan (2020) econometric model found

that these companies likely benefit most from Open Access, because they require access to robust and specific scientific knowledge, but are too small for pricey subscriptions. Focusing on small and medium sized pharmaceuticals companies, ElSabry & Sumikura (2020) applied a regression model on 918 patents and also suggest that smaller companies benefit from Open Access. In particular, they found a positive Open Access effect on small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) without collaborators at universities or other public research institutions that usually can make use of subscribed journals.

2.4 Evidence-base associated with patents and scientific non-patent references (SNPR)

A recurring theme in the quantitative study of patent citations is the difficulty of identifying NPL generally and SNPR in particular. NPL are provided as text strings, making it difficult to analyse them. In his review, van Raan (2017) reports on efforts to develop databases for patent citation analysis since the 1980s, carried out at the Institut für Scientific Information (Philadelphia, USA), the Dutch Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), the Belgian KU Leuven and the German Fraunhofer Society.

In recent years, the application of big data analytics tools for patent citation analysis can be observed. The German Competence Centre for Bibliometrics launched a pilot, mapping patent data with the Web of Science, applying a Solr full text search procedure on the DOCDB, the EPO core reference raw data product (Knaus & Palzenberger 2018). After manually checking a random sample of 1,000 candidate records, they were confident that they successfully matched more than six million unique NPL to journal articles indexed in the Web of Science. Using a similar approach, Jefferson et al. (2018) were able to resolve 14.1 million SNPR from the DOCDB. Instead of using the proprietary Web of Science, they queried openly available scholarly datasets from Crossref and Pubmed / PubMed Central. The findings are made publicly available through the discovery service *lens.org*, which allows search queries results for inventions that referenced scholarship.

3 Data and methods

For this deliverable, we collected data relating to Open Science practices in innovation with a particular focus on Open Access by drawing on publicly available data sources. We extracted and normalized NPL, and matched them with big scholarly data comprising Open Access status information in order to obtain a subset of SNPR. We identified patents with NPL through Google Patents, a large structured text corpus of patent grants and applications. Because NPL in Google Patents are only represented as text strings, thus lacking structured bibliographic metadata, we extracted unique identifiers used by Unpaywall, a popular Open Access discovery service, and the subject-specific repositories PubMed and arXiv. After reference matching with these scholarly datasets, we were able to determine SNPL resources including their Open Access status. The workflow involved a number of steps specific to the patent database and scholarly data sources that can be summarised as follows (see Table 1).

3.1 Google Patents

First, we identified patents with NPL through the Google Patents data snapshot accessible on Google Big Query², last modified on 13 May 2021. We restricted our search to patent families, defined as “a collection of patent applications covering the same or similar technical content”³, that were published between 2010 and 2020, and determined the number of patent families with at least one NPL. At the time of writing, Google Patents includes over 120 million patent publications from 100+ patent offices around the world.⁴

Although other search engines exist that link patents to NPL and SNPL like *lens.org*, we used Google Patents because of its analytical interface provided by Google Big Query, a high-performant cloud-based database for big data analytics. The database interface allows querying NPL in-text citations with SQL. This enabled us to query the Google patent corpus with regular expressions indicating typically used identifiers to refer to scholarly publications without setting up an own computing environment to analyze large amounts of patent bulk data. Then, we parsed the obtained identifiers with regular expressions from the unstructured text-strings and collated them into one dataset using the following scholarly data sources.

3.2 Unpaywall (DOI)

As a first type of identifier, we searched for Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), a widely used mechanism to provide unambiguous and long-lasting linking to scholarly work. DOIs have become the *de facto* standard not only to cite, but also to interlink different versions and (metadata) representations of scholarly work. Most prominently, the DOI registration agency Crossref serves all major scholarly publishers. Crossref provides comprehensive article-level metadata through openly available APIs (Hendricks et al. 2020). Because of its coverage and re-use opportunities, Crossref is an essential data source in the quantitative study of scholarly communications, either directly (Hendricks et al. 2020), or as part of aggregated data sources, for which Unpaywall is a prominent example (Piwowar et al. 2018).

² <https://cloud.google.com/blog/topics/public-datasets/google-patents-public-datasets-connecting-public-paid-and-private-patent-data>

³ <https://www.epo.org/searching-for-patents/helpful-resources/first-time-here/patent-families.html>

⁴ <https://support.google.com/faqs/answer/7049585>

Here, and in line with work carried out in D3.2, we used Unpaywall to determine SNPR including their Open Access status.⁵ This Open Access discovery service checks for links to openly available full texts for all DOIs registered by Crossref (Piwowar et al. 2018). To prepare the match with Unpaywall using DOIs, we extracted syntactically valid DOI patterns using the R package `biblids` (Held 2021). Then, we obtained metadata from Unpaywall using the parsed DOIs. We used the publicly available Unpaywall dump from July 2021, restricting ourselves to publications published after 2008. To allow for efficient data manipulation and retrieval, we imported the Unpaywall dump to Google BigQuery.

3.3 Europe PubMed Central (PMID, PMCID)

Not all scholarly literature is referenced by DOIs, but researchers make use of other types of unique identifiers. In biomedicine and the life sciences, the use of the PubMed identifiers is a common practise to provide references to scientific articles. PubMed is a widely used and comprehensive literature database of research articles in these fields.⁶ Following previous SNPR reference matching approaches that complement DOIs with PubMed identifiers (Jefferson et al. 2018), we queried Google Patents Big Query interface for the standard identifiers PMID and PMCID. While the former represents metadata about a scholarly publication in PubMed, the latter provides linkage to PubMed Central, a free full text archive of PubMed-indexed literature. Again, we started by querying the NPL in-text citations for patterns indicating PMIDs and PMCIDs. Next, we extracted candidate IDs using regular expressions. The matching to PubMed / PubMed Central was carried out by retrieving metadata from Europe PMC, which is a PubMed mirror and allows to search PubMed metadata and the PubMed Central repository simultaneously (Ferguson et al. 2021). During this automated matching, we used the R package `europemc` (Jahn 2021) that interfaces the Europe PMC REST API. Data matching with Europe PMC was carried out on 31 August 2021.

3.4 arXiv (arXiv ID)

Because of the prominence of arXiv in the information seeking behaviour of SMEs revealed by ON-MERRIT D4.2 “Drivers and barriers to uptake of Open Science resources in industry”, we expanded our analysis to this widely popular repository. arXiv, launched in 1991, is an open-access repository for scholarly articles in the fields of physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, statistics, electrical engineering and systems science, and economics⁷. Similar to the situation in biomedicine and the life sciences, citing an arXiv document through a unique identifier is recommended. The canonical form of arXiv ID is a sequence of alphanumeric code starting with “arxiv:”⁸. After retrieving relevant text strings from Google Patents Big Query corpus using patterns resembling arXiv IDs, we extracted the IDs and validated them against the arXiv metadata API. Here, we used the R package `arXiv` for programmatic access to the freely available arXiv API (Ram & Bromann 2021).

Table 1 presents results for each workflow step and data source.

⁵ <https://unpaywall.org/>

⁶ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

⁷ <https://arxiv.org/>

⁸ https://arxiv.org/help/arxiv_identifier

Source	ID type	Google Patents re-trieved		Number of IDs ex-tracted and matched		Works published be-tween 2008-2020	
		In-text ci-tations	Patent Families	Unique IDs	Patent Families	Unique IDs	Patent Families
Unpaywall	DOI	594,094	240,010	415,148	230,108	204,847	137,498
arXiv	arXiv ID	25,571	14,983	8,469	8,317	8,317	9,523
Europe PMC	PMID/PMCID	11,134	4,122	7,284	3,974	2,801	1,862
Total		-	-	-	-	215,962	146,382

Table 1: Overview Results of data analytics workflow to query, extract and find scholarly work through the matching with scholarly data sources. Patent applications were published between 2010 and 2020. Eligible publications had to be published between 2008 and 2020.

3.5 Open Access evidence

Drawing on the compiled data allowed us not only to investigate the prevalence of Open Access resources in our sample, but also the type of Open Access provision. Here, we drew on Unpaywall’s classification of the Open Access host, which distinguishes between publisher and repository-provided Open Access. Because versions of the Open Access full text can be provided by publishers and repositories at the same time, we distinguished between Open Access full texts provided only by publisher (“Publisher only”) or repositories (“Repositories only”), or both (“Publisher & Repositories”). We extended this classification to SNPR linked to Europe PMC. PMC largely consists of full texts, which were made freely available in collaboration with publishers (Ferguson et al. 2021). Therefore, we coded Open Access full texts in PMC as (“Publisher & Repositories”). SNPR indexed in the arxiv were coded as (“Repositories only”), although a considerable number of journals in subjects covered by the arxiv have become Open Access as well (Gentil-Beccot, Mele & Brooks 2009). However, the data did not allow us to determine this overlap sufficiently.

3.6 Matching references beyond unique identifiers

Initially, we intended to match in-text references beyond unique identifiers to increase the coverage of our analysis. To this end, we tried to extract relevant bibliographic information from text strings. The strings commonly had the following format:

```
[Author name(s): ["Title"], [Journal Title], [vol / issue nr.], [date], [page nrs.], [ISSN], [DOI]
```

Examples:

```
M. DEKIEVIET ET AL.: "Design and performance of a highly efficient mass spectrometer for molecular beams", REVIEW OF SCIENTIFIC INSTRUMENTS, vol. 71, no. 5, May 2000 (2000-05-01), pages 2015 - 2018, XP012038271, DOI: 10.1063/1.1150570
```

PORCELLI,S.; YOCKEY,C.E.; BRENNER,M.B.; BALK,S.P.: "Analysis of T cell antigen receptor (TCR) expression by human peripheral blood CD4-8- alpha/beta T cells demonstrates preferential use of several V beta genes and an invariant TCR alpha chain", J. EXP. MED., vol. 178, 1993, pages 1 - 16, XP002104251, DOI: doi:10.1084/jem.178.1.1

We hence began extracting relevant information according to item position and format (e.g., author(s), title, DOI, ISSN). However, we soon realised that many of the text strings had a much shorter format with very little information, as seen in the below examples:

SCHMIDT ET AL., DIABETOLOGIA, vol. 28, 1985, pages 704
BOERNER ET AL., J. IMMUNOL., vol. 147, no. 1, 1991, pages 86 - 95

We therefore opted to classify the strings into either this short format or any other format. Extraction of this second format commenced in a similar manner as before, detecting authors, journal, volume, and year.

We then assessed levels of precision and recall for this admittedly limited approach, with encouraging results. To assess these values, we sampled 100 text strings and compared the extracted elements with the raw text string.

To evaluate the predictions, we used the following common terminology (Nadeau & Sekine 2007):

- The number of correct predictions (COR)
- The number of actual predictions (ACT)
- The number of possible predictions (POS)

Precision is then defined as COR / ACT , while *recall* is defined as COR / POS .

We evaluated the 100 text strings manually, leading to a precision of 97.80% and a recall of 78.19%. The main reason for the lower recall were references to publication types other than journals, such as book chapters, database entries, conference proceedings, etc.

Although this approach seems promising, we were unable to pursue it further within this current study due to resource constraints within the project. We hence leave this for future research. The script for the extraction of bibliometric information⁹, as well as the notebook documenting the evaluation¹⁰ are available on GitHub.

3.7 Data and code availability

Throughout this exploratory data analysis, we used the R programming language, version 4.1. To allow for high-performance and remote data access, we used Google Big Query. Notebooks and data can be found here: https://github.com/on-merrit/patent_exploration

⁹ https://github.com/on-merrit/patent_exploration/blob/master/extract_references/extract_reference_parts.py

¹⁰ https://github.com/on-merrit/patent_exploration/blob/master/ep_npl_eval.md

4 Results

This section first presents the results of our large-scale analysis with a view on patent families published between 2010 and 2020 with reference to non-patent literature (NPL) by year, inventor countries and patent subject. Then, we present a more detailed analysis of our compiled data about scientific non-patent references (SNPR), that we obtained by parsing unique identifiers from in-text patent citations, which could be mapped to scholarly work published between 2008-2020. The focus of the SNPR analysis is on the OA uptake by year and type of provision relative to the country of affiliation of the inventor and patent subjects.

4.1 Coverage of non-patent literature (NPL)

4.1.1 Overview

Between 2010 and 2020, Google Patents comprised 22,186,393 published patent families. Of these, 7,681,566 had at least one citation to NPL, representing a share of 36%. In total, we found 24,752,870 unique NPL text strings in the investigated period. On average, 8.23 NPL text strings were cited per patent family with NPL. The median number of NPL citations was 2, the maximum number of NPL citations was 10,645.

Figure 1 presents the yearly distribution of the number of issued patents by year of publication, suggesting a steady growth of patent families, although its number decreased since 2018, presumably because of an indexing lag in Google Patents. Figure 1 also shows a proportional decrease of NPL. This lag between the publication date of patents and the inclusion of NPL is not surprising, because scholarly work supporting patents can be provided after the publication of a patent (Guerrero-Bote, Moed, & De-Moya-Anegón 2021).

Figure 1: Patent families with reference to at least one non-patent literature (NPL) between 2010 and 2020. Blue area shows the absolute number of patent families with at least one NPL, the grey area illustrates the overall number of patent families.

4.1.2 NPL coverage by subject

Table 2 provides a breakdown by the nine main sections of the Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC), an extension of the International Patent Classification (IPC), jointly curated by the European Patent Office (EPO) and the US Patent and Trademark Office (UPTO).¹¹ Between 2010 and 2020, the CPC sections “G - Physics” and “H - Electricity” recorded the most patent families as well as NPL citations, while the NPL percentage among these fields was close to the overall NPL uptake. Patent families classified in the CPC sections “C - Chemistry; metallurgy” and “A - Human necessities” had the highest NPL percentage. Interestingly, the NPL percentage varies considerably among the CPC sections, ranging from 20.67% in the main section “E - Fixed constructions” to 52.20% in “C - Chemistry”.

CPC section	Patent families	with NPL	in%
A - Human necessities	2,553,254	1,084,538	42.48
B - Performing operations; transporting	3,251,311	831,292	25.57
C - Chemistry; metallurgy	2,306,879	1,204,100	52.20

¹¹ <https://www.epo.org/searching-for-patents/helpful-resources/first-time-here/classification/cpc.html>
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D - Textiles; paper	221,382	64,915	29.32
E - Fixed constructions	657,813	135,954	20.67
F - Mechanical engineering; lighting; heating; weapons; blasting engines or pumps	1,631,687	346,164	21.22
G - Physics	4,410,801	1,744,117	39.54
H - Electricity	4,265,802	1,463,138	34.30
Y - General	2,295,435	807,348	35.17

Table 2: Overview patent families with NPL 2010 -2020 by the Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC). Note that a patent family can belong to more than one CPC section. Here, we present full counts.

Figure 2 presents the distribution of NPL per CPC main sections, highlighting the median and the range between the 10th and 90th percentile. The median number of NPL was either 2 or 3, while considerable variations exist relative to the observed number of NPL. Values from the 90th percentile range from 8 NPL citations per patent family in the CPC sections “D - Textiles; paper”, “E - Fixed constructions”, and “F - Mechanical engineering; lighting; heating; weapons; blasting engines or pumps” to 32 in “A - Human necessities”.

Figure 2: Distribution of the number of NPL strings per patent family by Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) main section, visualized as a diminutive distribution chart, highlighting the range between 10th and 90th percentile, as well as the median for each CPC main section. Note that patent families without NPL were excluded.

4.1.3 NPL coverage by inventor countries

Table 3 presents a breakdown of patents with citations to NPL by inventor countries. Note that for most patent families, no geographic information was provided. Google Patents covers most patents from inventors from the US, followed by the Asian countries South Korea and Japan. Germany ranks fourth as the first European country with 711,766 patent families invented. Like in the distribution among CPC sections, we observe large NPL share variations, ranging between 11% (South Korea) and 51% (United States).

Country	Patent families	with NPL	in%
No Info	13,415,994	2,185,384	16.29
United States	1,944,038	994,604	51.16
South Korea	1,473,120	163,924	11.13
Japan	887,836	425,645	47.94
Germany	711,766	231,838	32.57
Taiwan	347,836	45,878	13.19
France	244,127	100,455	41.15
Russia	235,076	81,241	34.56
China	220,861	96,735	43.80
United Kingdom	147,642	64,763	43.86
Other	1,184,180	439,146	37.08

Table 3: Overview patent families with NPL 2010 -2020 by the countries of the inventors, ranked by the number of patent families per country. Note that a patent family can have inventors from different countries. Here, we present full counts.

In the following, Figure 3 presents the distribution of the number of NPL text strings per patent family by inventor's country for the top nine countries, highlighting the range between the 10th and 90th percentile. Note that we excluded patent families without NPL. Patent families representing inventions from the United States show the largest variations. On average, as represented by the median NPL number per patent family, a patent family from the United States cited five NPL, while the median NPL number for patent families from South Korea, Japan, and Germany is 2.

Figure 3: Distribution of the number of NPL strings per patent family by the countries of the inventors, visualized as a diminutive distribution chart, highlighting the range between 10th and 90th percentile, as well as the median for the top nine countries in terms of published patent families. Note that patent families without NPL were excluded.

4.2 Open access to scientific non-patent references (SNPR)

4.2.1 Overview

Mapping unique identifiers parsed from NPL text strings and resolving them against Unpaywall, Europe PMC and arXiv offers insight into the extent to which SNPR are Open Access. First, we will explore the share of Open Access. Then, we will provide an overview about the Open Access venues. Overall, we were able to identify 96,228 SNPR with an Open Access full text, representing an Open Access availability rate of 45%.

Figure 4 illustrates the number of SNPR in our sample by Open Access availability over the years. It reveals that the majority of scholarly publications in our sample were published before 2015. As expected, Figure 4 suggests an increasing share of Open Access for more recent publications. Open Access uptake rates grew from 35% in 2008 to 82% in 2020. Note that the total number of SNPR in our sample decreased over time. In conjunction with the small number of normalized SNPR relative to the overall number of NPL text strings in our sample, these data artifacts necessitate a careful interpretation of our results.

Figure 4: Development of the number of scientific non-patent references (SNPR) by Open Access status and year.

In terms of publication types, most scholarly works in the sample were journal articles ($n = 175,361$, 81%), followed by conference proceedings articles ($n = 28,977$, 13%) and preprints ($n = 8,489$, 4%) (see Table 4). The table also illustrates large variations relative to the Open Access share by publication type. All preprints were openly available, followed by journal articles and proceedings articles.¹²

Publication type	All		Open Access	
	NPL	in%	NPL	in%
journal article	175,361	81.20	81,759	46.62
proceedings article	28,977	13.42	4,927	17.00

¹² One preprint, which is accessible under <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv.7764638.v1>, posted to chemrxiv.org was tagged as closed access by Unpaywall, although it is provided under a CC-BY license. We changed the status of this preprint to Open Access for the purpose of this analysis.

preprints	8,489	3.93	8,489	100
Other	3,135	1.45	1,053	33.59

Table 4: Open access to text-mined NPL by publication types, 2008 - 2020.

Interestingly, SNPR not only included preprints from the arxiv.org (n = 8,317), but also from other subject-specific preprint archives, in particular the bioRxiv (n = 154), which targets research in biology and the life sciences.¹³ Launched in 2013, the bioRxiv gained popularity recently as a platform to rapidly communicate life science research related to the COVID pandemic. This trend can be also observed in our data: 33 recently published bioRxiv preprints, which were cited in patents, are related to COVID research.

Figure 5 presents the yearly Open Access uptake in SNPR in comparison to the overall Open Access distribution in Unpaywall, restricting the analysis to journal articles, the most prevalent publication type in Unpaywall (n = 41,207,091, 70%), and in our SNPR sample (n = 175,361, 81%). Figure 5 reveals that the SNPR Open Access share is larger than the overall average across journals. However, the yearly distribution follows the general trend that an increasing proportion of journal articles become openly available. The peak in 2020 in the SNPR Open Access percentage might be due to a data artifact; only a small number of articles from the year 2020 was cited in patents.

Figure 5: Yearly development of openly available non-patent literature (NPL) in comparison to the total. Data source: Unpaywall dump from July 2021. Note that only journal articles were investigated.

¹³ <https://www.biorxiv.org/ON-MERRIT-824612>

4.2.2 Citation windows

Previous studies reported a considerable time-lag until SNPR were cited in patents, which needs to be considered when investigating the Open Access uptake in patents. Figure 6 shows the yearly differences between the SNPR and patent families' publication year. The median lag between the SNPR publication and that of the patent is 5 years. It must be noted, however, that only SNPR citations from 2008 onwards were included, presumably underestimating the overall lag. A few patent families refer to SNPR published after the patent, highlighting that SNPR can be also provided after the publication of a patent.

Figure 6: Time lag between the year of publication of scientific non-patent references (SNPR) and the patent citation. Yellow dotted line shows the median difference of five years, highlighting that 50% of the SNPR were cited within five years after initial publication. Note that we only considered SNPR published between 2008 and 2020.

Figure 7 presents the yearly differences between publication dates by scholarly data sources. SNPR to scholarly work provided by arXiv show a lesser yearly delay than publications with DOI or PMID/PMCID. Interestingly, Europe PMC accounts for a considerable number of articles that were published and thus cited after the patent publication in contrast to the general trend.

Yearly lag between SNPR publication and citation in patent

Figure 7: Density estimates of the time lag between the year of publication of scientific non-patent references (SNPR) and patent citation by scholarly data source. Note that we only considered SNPR published between 2008 and 2020.

4.2.3 SNPR Open Access share by main subject

Figure 8: Open access to scientific non-patent references (SNPR) by Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) main sections published between 2008 and 2020. Labels show the total number of NPL in our sample, while blue bars present the Open Access percentage per CPC main section. Yellow dotted line shows the overall Open Access percentage.

Figure 8 presents the SNPR Open Access percentage by CPC main section in comparison to the overall share. While patent families belonging to the CPC main sections “A - Human necessities” (56%), “C - Chemistry; metallurgy” (52%) and “G - Physics” (49%) were above average. “D - Textiles; paper” (25%) and “E - Fixed constructions” (25%) had a considerably lower Open Access share. Likewise, patent families belonging to these CPC main sections were represented to a lesser extent in our NPL data in terms of the total number of identified NPL, presumably because of the overall low NPL coverage in these fields (see Table 2).

4.2.4 SNPR Open Access share by the country of the inventor

Furthermore, our compiled data provides insights into the Open Access shares by the inventor countries. Figure 9 illustrates the Open Access percentage for the top nine countries in terms of patent families published (see Table 3). Patents invented in the United States (55%) and United Kingdom (54%) had an above-average share of openly available SNPR. Although represented to a similar extent in terms of identified and mapped NPL citations, Germany (43%) showed a larger Open Access uptake than Japan (39%) and France (38%).

Figure 9: Open access to scientific non-patent references (SNPR) by the countries of the inventors, ranked by the total number of patent families per country between 2010 and 2020. Labels show the total number of NPL in our sample, while blue bars present the Open Access percentage per country. Yellow dotted line shows the overall Open Access percentage. SNPR were published between 2008 and 2020.

4.2.5 Open Access by provider

Overall, most Open Access SNPR in our sample were provided by both a publisher and repositories (n = 43,475, 45%). 39% of Open Access SNPR were only available through repositories (n = 37,511) and 16% through publisher websites only (n = 15,242). Figure 10 presents the yearly distribution of Open Access host types relative to the total number of Open Access articles in our sample.

Figure 10: Relative development of openly available scientific non-patent references (SNPR) by years and the Open Access host.

Figure 11 provides a breakdown by CPC main section. It illustrates that the majority of Open Access SNPR was hosted by repositories across all CPC main sections, either solely or in combination with an Open Access journal publication. Interestingly, CPC section with a relatively large proportion of full texts, which were only made openly accessible through repositories, were “H - Electricity” (n = 8,148, p = 59%), “B - Performing operations; transporting” (n = 3,912, 47%) and “G - Physics” (n = 20,593, 46%).

Figure 11: Open Access to scientific non-patent references (SNPR OA) by Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) main sections and host type. Labels show the total number of Open Access SNPR in our sample, while coloured bars present the breakdown by Open Access host per CPC main section.

Figure 12 presents a breakdown by country of the patent inventors. Again, no considerable variations relative to the overall trend could be observed, although the proportion of Open Access SNPR only hosted by a repository is somewhat lower among patent families from Russia.

Figure 12: Open Access to scientific non-patent references (SNPR OA) by the countries of the inventors, ranked by the number of patent families per country, and host type. Labels show the total number of Open Access SNPR in our sample, while coloured bars present the breakdown by Open Access host per country.

5 Discussion

The purpose of this deliverable is to present a large-scale view of the state of citation practices within patents to non-patent literature (NPL), and especially use of OA resources among scientific non-patent references (SNPR), by exploiting openly available big data sources. Overall, we find that around one third of patent families were supported by at least one NPL, although the number of references per patent family can vary considerably across subjects and inventor countries, which is in accordance with previous research (Jefferson et al (2018).

To obtain the SNPR Open Access status, we parsed unique identifiers representing scientific work from the Google Patents corpus and matched them with the scholarly data sources Unpaywall, Europe PMC and arXiv. In doing so, we were able to compile a data sample comprising 215,962 SNPR, which were cited by 146,382 patent families. Overall, we find that nearly half of all identifiable SNPR in our sample are openly available.

Our findings suggest an Open Access citation advantage in patents. Over the years, the Open Access rate for SNPR representing journal articles was above that of Unpaywall, a major OA discovery service, indicating that openly available scientific articles are more likely cited in patents. In line with previous research, we found considerable disciplinary and country-specific variations (Severin et al. 2020, Huang et al. 2020, Robinson-Garcia, Costas & van Leeuwen 2020). Concerning differences between countries, it is interesting to speculate here about the extent to which these differences are due to differences in levels of access to scientific literature for the innovators themselves, or whether they might also reflect the extent to which examiners from patent offices adding references themselves can access the evidence. Unfortunately, our data does not allow us to draw any conclusions on this point, but we flag it here as a possible route for future research.

Concerning disciplinary differences, it is interesting to note that patents belonging to the CPC section “A human necessities” stand out, which covers fields of innovation linked to sustainable development goals (SDG) like agriculture, food and health. These patents show not only a stronger link to research in terms of the penetration of SNPR, but also to research that is openly available. This is in line with previous research. Piwowar found the highest Open Access rate among scientific articles published in biomedicine journals (Piwowar et al. 2018).

Only a few studies have attempted to measure the impact of Open Access on innovation through examining patents citing NPL. Drawing on a sample of 43 prestigious life science journals that published 132,872 research articles between 2005 and 2012 and U.S. patent applications since 2005, Bryan and Ozcan (2020) found a slight positive effect of the Open Access mandate of the NIH to the citation of SNPR. NIH-funded research was cited much more often after the introduction of the NIH research, ranging between 12% and 27%. Similarly, ElSabry and Sumikura (2020) observed an increasing uptake of articles from Open Access journals in patents from American pharmaceutical companies. In line with our findings, they observed considerable variations by subject.

Although a majority of bibliometric studies suggest an Open Access citation advantage (Langham-Putrow, Bakker & Riegelman 2021), potential biases need to be considered, both relative to scholarly communication in general and to patent citation in particular. Our observed Open Access citation advantage could be explained by the selection bias according to which authors tend to make their work openly available, where they expect most impact in terms of citations (Eysenbach 2006). Previous research found a substantial body

of author-inventor self-citations across SNPR. Inventors tend not only to cite their own work, but also scientific articles from their country (Tijseen 2001). Moreover, inventors tend to cite background work to demonstrate knowledge, while research directly linked to the invention is cited to a lesser extent. Furthermore, previous research highlights a considerable link between the country affiliation of an invention and the cited SNPR. National policies and Open Access funder mandates have strongly influenced how this publishing model is implemented, resulting in varying country-specific uptake rates. We found particularly strong uptake rates among inventions from the US and UK. Particularly British universities had the largest share of OA publications, but also the US ranked above the global average (Robinson-Garcia, Costas & van Leeuwen 2020).

In contrast to previous research, our study is not limited to journal articles, but also takes other types of scholarly work into account. This hence presents a key contribution of this study. We were able to confirm the use of preprints in the information seeking behaviour in industry. Not only preprints from the well-established arXiv (see D4.2) were cited by unique identifiers, but also preprints from the bioRxiv, which, together with the sister repository medRxiv, has gained prominence since COVID-19 for accelerated communication of scientific results (Fraser et al. 2021). Contrasting the lag between preprint publication and citation in a patent furthermore suggest that preprints are cited timelier in patents than other types of scholarly work. However, previous research highlighted the large proportion of delayed Open Access. Indeed, a considerable proportion of Open Access articles indexed in Unpaywall was made available after an embargo period (Piwowar, Priem & Orr 2019).

We also considered different ways of providing Open Access, whereas ElSabry and Sumikura (2020) focused on Open Access Journals only and Bryan and Ozcan (2020) on the discipline-specific repository PubMed Central. Our findings show that Open Access provided by repositories is most common, although many OA SNPR were provided by both repositories and journals (Larivière & Sugimoto 2018). This implies that inventors and patent examiners could have benefited from a diverse landscape of Open Access publishing options, which are not limited to publishing in journals. Indeed, patent offices already make use of federated Open Access discovery during the patent examination. The most widely used tool for searching and retrieving scientific articles at the EPO is Google Scholar, Scopus and PubMed. All these discovery solutions currently provide unified access to various Open Access publishing services (Verbandt & Vadot 2018).

This deliverable extends ON-MERRIT's literature review (D4.1) and survey (D4.2) on the drivers and barriers to uptake of Open Science resources in industry with quantitative evidence. We can confirm the growing role of Open Science practices in innovation by highlighting increasing Open Access uptake rates in SNPR. We also found evidence that novel publication practises, like rapid publication of results through preprints in the life sciences, have been picked up in innovation. Our data suggests that citing preprints disseminated in the fields of physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, statistics, electrical engineering and systems science, and economics through arXiv is well established. However, our data is unable to distinguish patents from SMEs/industry on the one hand and academic institutions on the other, an important data point because D4.2 has shown that the academic background positively influences the uptake of open science practices in innovation. Also, SMEs tend to be more affected from lacking access to scientific articles (ElSabry and Sumikura 2020). Furthermore, our data did not map patents with scholarly publication activities of innovators at the organizational level due to a lack of fine-grained geolocation data about inventor and application locations (de Rassenfosse, Kozak and Seliger 2019).

Future studies on the information seeking behaviour in SMEs relative to Open Access should seek to closer align qualitative and quantitative approaches. We recommend to restrict further studies to a representative sample of patent inventors and to specifically ask them for their citation motivation after an in-depth analysis of the characteristics of NPL and SNPR in their patents. Similarly, to extend a large-scale research design as presented here, we would focus on specific subjects and institutions to gain more evidence about the potential role of open science practices in innovation in a particular domain of interest.

Patent analysis that draws on SNPR is very laborious because of the lack of linkage to standardized scholarly data. We recommend to include unique identifiers in the SNPR citations to allow for improved detection of the influence of scholarly publications on innovation. Unique identification is not only required to scholarly publications, but also to organisations. Here, more effort is needed to identify and disambiguate the contributing inventors and applicants.

Future studies will likely benefit from such improved evidence base associated with Open Access and patents. During the course of our work, the search engine lens.org has started to offer bulk download of its underlying data for academic use. In its data, metadata about patent families is linked to disambiguated bibliographic metadata and includes Open Access status information. But also, public patent offices curate large databases about NPL. Bulk access, as in the case of the EPO worldwide bibliographic data (DOCDB), for large-scale analytical purposes, is not directly possible. Given the importance of monitoring the influence of science on innovation, we recommend that these essential data sources will be made available without restrictions to the public, ideally in cloud-based big data analytics environments like Google Big Query.

6 Conclusion

Open Access literature is a widely used and reputable source for scientific information in innovation. Our big data analysis shows an Open Access advantage for patents between 2010 and 2020, meaning that the share of Open Access among scientific non-patent references in patents was above the general trend. Combining structured patent data with scholarly data sources with a focus on Open Access opens up the opportunity to better understand patterns of adoption of Open Science practises relative to scholarly publishing. In this regard, and in line with the literature review conducted, we found the comparison across countries of inventors and technological fields as promising indicators to analyse the Open Access uptake in innovation.

While our data analysis suggests that scientific articles cited in patents are more likely openly available in comparison to the general trend, it is challenging to link it to specific science policies and incentives. Overall, analysing the nature of science-technology linkage particularly with regard to Open Science is complex, requiring more research on the role of Open Science resources in the information seeking of innovators. Meanwhile, there are notable activities to interlink patent information with big scholarly data both in academia and in industry. These activities promise an improved evidence-base and monitoring system to measure technology-science linkage with a focus on Open Access and Open Science, if the legal and socio-economical context of patent citations is taken into account.

6.1 Limitations

Our study is limited in various aspects. One and most important is that non-patent literature (NPL) citations are only accessible as text strings, which need to be parsed and mapped to scholarly data sources. So far, no openly available evidence base exists to measure the influence of Open Access to the scholarly literature on patents. Lens.org provides a graphical user interface to analyse scientific non-patent literature (SNPR) citations to Open Access documents, but it is not suitable for large-scale analyses as presented here. Because of the large number of patent citations manual matching would not be possible. The limited resources of our work furthermore prevented us from expanding our method by drawing on an increasing number of reference matching and text classification approaches like BERT (Voskuil & Verberne 2021). Instead, we made use of identifiers cited in the NPL sections and the mapping to publicly available scholarly data sources. It must be noted, however, that our investigated data sources are selective towards scholarly journals, while lacking other important NPL types, particularly grey literature like technical documentations or standards. In fact, only a small proportion of NPL strings contained an identifier like a DOI, which is widely common in scholarly publishing, but less, for instance, in the grey literature field.

Furthermore, we lack evidence about how valid our SNPR sample is to draw conclusions about the information seeking behaviour of inventors. We have no evidence about who cited the NPL, and when. Was the work cited by the inventor, or did it happen through the patent office? We also lack information about the availability of discovery solutions. For instance, the European Patent Office added more and more scholarly literature databases in prior art search, including Open Access full text databases (Verbandt & Vadot 2018), which might have led to an increase in citations to openly available SNPR. Moreover, due to our research design, we did not test how representative our sample is. Therefore, careful interpretation of our findings is needed, when drawing general conclusions about the Open Access uptake in the SNPR.

6.2 Recommendations

Building on the discussion presented above, we offer the following set of preliminary recommendations to OS/RRR policy-makers (funders and governments), academic and scientific institutional leaders, and researchers. (These recommendations will be refined during the synthesis phase of ON-MERRIT, which will include co-creation processes with these three stakeholder groups.)

Science policy:

- Openly available scientific articles contribute substantially to innovation, suggesting that innovators are less dependent upon costly journal subscriptions. However, policy makers must assume that the discovery of relevant resources to innovation can still be resource-intensive for inventors and examiners alike. Particularly, the increasing uptake of new Open Science practices like preprints in the life sciences as response to the COVID pandemic needs to be reflected. We therefore recommend close monitoring of internal and external discovery solutions in this regard.
- The increasing amount of publicly-available data around scholarly publications and patents promises effective monitoring systems to measure technology-science linkage. Because of the varying motivations for citing scientific articles in patents, however, monitoring exercises using big data analytics need to be complemented by qualitative approaches and in-depth studies in order to provide a robust evidence base for science and innovation policies.
- Efficiency and quality in the analysis of scientific impact in patents would be significantly improved if patents referenced literature using structured metadata. Science policy-makers should work with policy-makers responsible for innovation regulations to encourage reform and uptake in this regard.

Institutions:

- Open Access resources are well covered in patents. Because of the diverse nature of Open Access publishing, we recommend dedicated information literacy programs for innovators at academic institutions focusing on the discovery and use of Open Access resources in patenting.
- Research suggests that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) substantially benefit from collaborations with universities regarding the access and discovery of scientific resources. Institutions should further promote collaboration with SMEs as they can result in innovations, which are more strongly based on scientific evidence.

Researchers:

- Researchers should be aware that Open Access literature seems to have an above-average impact on scientific innovation as measured by citations in patents to incentivise further OA uptake.
- Open Access resources, particularly preprints, are widely cited and thus are considered public disclosures in patenting. Researchers aiming at patents can thus draw on an increasing amount of openly available resources to support claims made in patents. For this, we recommend making use of new discovery solutions that interlink patent information systems with scholarly literature like lens.org.
- Likewise, research on the science-technology linkage can exploit an increasing amount of structured data for in their research design. In order to assure the quality of patent citation analytics, we recommend comparative studies of increasingly popular big data sources and open methodologies.

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